

Elite Healers Sports Massage is more than just a massage, it's therapy. They are setting a higher standard in the world of massage therapy. Elite Healers Sports Massage services in NYC include: Sports Massage Therapy, Medical Massage Therapy, Deep Tissue Massage Therapy, Swedish Massage Therapy, Thai Massage, and Chair Massage Office Events. They provide recovery for athletes of all levels with Sports Massage. They also help people manage chronic muscle pain, recover from injuries, recover from surgery and help to provide muscle relief to those who just have regular muscle aches and pains by providing medical massage services as well. You can book a 60, 90, or 120 minute session. Visit the Elite Healers Sports Massage website at <https://www.elitehealerssportsmassage.com> to book an appointment or to see their hours of operation.

Now that you know more about Elite Healers Sports Massage, let's talk about massage therapy benefits. More and more people are finding that massage therapy offers a wide range of benefits, from relieving stress to helping with certain health conditions. It is a [Medical Massage NYC](#) practice that has been around for thousands of years and is one of the oldest forms of healing.

Benefits of Massage for Pain Relief:

According to a study in the journal *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, massage can help ease muscle pain and stiffness caused by arthritis and other disorders. A massage reduces pain and inflammation in the affected area by releasing toxins, stimulating the release of endorphins and improving circulation to the muscle. The therapist also uses a variety of techniques, such as kneading, rocking, tapping, and holding steady pressure on the muscles. The technique used depends on the client's needs and physical condition, as well as the therapist's personal preferences. Many massage therapists are also licensed medical professionals who are qualified to prescribe medication and recommend other forms of treatment for patients with serious conditions or illness. Some insurance companies reimburse clients for massage therapy, and many doctors use it as a complementary treatment to manage their patients' conditions.

Relieves Headaches, Neck and Back Pain:

A study published in the *British Journal of Orthopedics* suggests that massage therapy may be a helpful way to reduce headaches. This is because it can calm the body and mind, reducing blood pressure and heart rate and affecting hormones that are associated with stress. Researchers believe this is because the pressure and massage stimulates the vagus nerve, which is part of the nervous system. This nerve connects the brain to the rest of the body and is important for sending signals to the muscles.

Getting a massage can also improve the flexibility of your joints, and increase your range of motion. This can lead to better performance in your everyday activities, like walking or sitting up straight in bed. It can also decrease the risk of developing injuries, as it increases your range of motion and reduces stress, which can cause injury. This is especially useful for athletes who are looking to improve their performance and reduce the chance of injury, the Cleveland Clinic says.

Relieves Insomnia, Helps You Sleep More Deeply:

A massage can help you get a deeper sleep by slowing your nervous system down and relieving the tension in your muscles. This can help you to fall asleep faster and stay asleep longer, a study in the journal *Sleep* found. If you have fibromyalgia, a chronic condition that causes muscle and joint pain, you can also improve your symptoms by getting regular massages. This is because the massage can relax the muscles, and it can also increase blood flow to the area, the Mayo Clinic explains.

The therapist also may use essential oils, such as lavender or peppermint. These oils are designed to relax the body and enhance the effects of the massage. It has become increasingly common for health insurance companies to cover massage, and more doctors are prescribing it as a treatment for chronic diseases or injuries. The American Massage Therapy Association estimates that 19 percent of Americans have received a massage in the last year, and more and more are aware of its many benefits. Now that you know more about the many benefits of massage therapy, it is time to go back to the website of Elite Healers Sports Massage to schedule an appointment today!